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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	Alterations in faecal microbiota composition, plasma lipids, and brain activity, suggest inter-connected pathways influencing malnutrition-associated cognitive and neurodevelopmental changes.		
Document creation date	12/10/2024	Corresponding Email	chris.pook@auckland.ac.nz
Principal investigator	Chris Pook	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Liggins Institute, The University of Auckland	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	1-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	No
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	-
1-phase system	3:5:4:1 BuOH:MeOH:chloroform:water	Derivatization	-

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	17500
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	3
Separation type 1	LC	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Centroid mode
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	2
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	Orbitrap	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	17500
MS vendor	Thermo	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	5
Ion source	ESI	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/editor/study/MT-BLS10066/descriptors	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

LEAP_S009 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S010 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S017 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S021 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S022 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S027 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S031 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S032 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S034 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S035 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S036 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S040 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S043 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S044 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S047 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S048 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S099 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S101 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S102 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S103 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S104 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S109 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S111 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S118 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S119 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S120 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S125 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S127 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S128 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S131 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S133 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S134 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S135 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S136 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S140 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S143 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S144 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S147 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S149 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S150 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S151 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S152 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S153 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S154 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S155 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S156 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S157 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S158 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S53 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S54 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S55 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S56 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S61 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S62 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S63 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S64 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S69 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S71 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S72 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S75 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S77 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S78 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S79 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S80 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S83 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S85 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S86 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S87 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S88 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S93 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S94 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S95 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP_S96 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S001 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S002 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S003 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S004 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S005 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S006 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S007 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S008 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S009 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S010 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S011 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S012 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S013 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S014 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S015 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S016 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S017 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S018 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S019 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S020 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S021 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S022 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S023 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S024 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S025 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S026 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S027 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S028 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S029 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S030 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S031 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S032 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S033 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S034 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S035 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S036 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S037 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S038 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S039 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S040 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S041 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S042 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S043 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S044 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S045 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S046 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S047 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S048 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S049 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S050 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S051 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S052 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S053 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S054 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S055 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S056 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S057 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S058 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S059 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S060 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S061 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S062 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S063 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S064 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S065 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S066 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S067 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S068 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S069 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S070 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S071 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S072 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S073 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S074 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S075 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S076 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S077 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S078 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S079 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

LEAP02_S80 / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	Room temperature
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Storage time (month)	0.0
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	10.0	Freeze-thaw cycles	0.0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30.0	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) MG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	MG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interfeerece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

1) MG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

2) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

2) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard Endogenous subclass			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

4) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

4) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

5) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

5) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

6) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

6) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

7) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

7) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
Endogenous subclass			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

8) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

8) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
	Endogenous subclass		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

9) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

9) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

10) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

10) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

11) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

11) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

12) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

12) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

13) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

13) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

14) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

14) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
	Endogenous subclass		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

15) FAHFA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FAHFA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

15) FAHFA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

16) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

16) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

17) LPC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

17) LPC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

18) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

18) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

19) PA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

19) PA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
Endogenous subclass			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

20) SM[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

20) SM[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

21) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

21) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

22) PG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

22) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
Endogenous subclass			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

23) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

23) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

24) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CL	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-2H]2-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

24) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
	Endogenous subclass		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

25) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

25) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

26) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

26) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard			
Endogenous subclass			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

27) Hex2Cer[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	No
Fragment name			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction, normalisation to internal standards, batch correction
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

27) Hex2Cer[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MS-DIAL
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		